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ABSTRACTS

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Enhancing Color Perception: Daltonization Software for Color Vision Deficiency

Harshraj Chundawat¹, Karan Varghese¹, Ketan Khatavkar¹ and Madhavi Bhongale^{1*}

¹School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research, MIT Art, Design and Technology University, Pune, India

*Corresponding author: madhavi.bhongale@mituniversity.edu.in

Abstract: Individuals with color vision deficiency (CVD), or color blindness, face challenges discerning specific hues due to the absence or malfunction of photoreceptor cells (cones) in the eyes. This study addresses prevalent types of CVD, affecting 8% of males and 0.5% of females, including Protanomaly/Protanopia, Deuteranomaly, Deuteranopia, Tritanomaly, Tritanopia, and Monochromacy. While primarily genetic, CVD can also result from various diseases. The study emphasizes the substantial impact of CVD on daily life, impacting color recognition, education, professional capabilities, safety, and psychosocial well-being. In response, we propose Daltonization, a sophisticated software solution that simulates a color-blind individual's perception of an image. The algorithm generates an error image by quantifying the difference between the original and simulated views, adjusting the original image based on these values to enhance color perception for individuals with CVD. This software-based approach offers a practical solution, contributing to inclusive visual communication and the improvement of daily experiences for individuals with color vision deficiency.

Keywords: Color Vision Deficiency (CVD), Daltonization, Photoreceptor Cells, RGB, LMS Transformation

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Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

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